

GRAMMATICAL PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATION

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ABSTRACT

This paper is devoted to examining grammatical problems in the translation process as well as considering the importance of grammar in this context. The key points of contention for translators are discussed, including fundamental grammatical problems such as differences between language structures. The syntactic aspects of translation are also discussed, including difficulties in translating long subordinate sentences and changes in word order. The translation of grammatical terms such as books and article structures is given particular attention. The use of context and the role of grammatical context in interpretation are discussed in detail.

The expression of grammatical meaning in translation must accurately reflect the original text's grammatical specificity, and this aspect leads to specific problems in translation between distant and unrelated languages. If we examine the problem of translation of sentences in English and Uzbek languages, it is necessary to mention the following characteristics:

- a) sentence has two parts: the possessive and the participle.
- b) sentence's verbal structure.
- c) having the participle in a stable place in the sentence.

Sentence structure and content in foreign and Uzbek languages.

Due to the fact that English, French and German languages belong to the Germanic group of Indo-European languages, and the Uzbek language belongs to the Turkish language group of the Altaic language family, their uniqueness is manifested primarily in the grammatical structure of these languages from the point of view of modern linguistics. In European languages, especially in German and English, the participle comes second after the possessive in the sentence (more precisely, the part of the participle comes after the possessive, and the adjective two or the infinitive form comes at the end of the sentence), in Turkish languages, including Uzbek, it is always comes at the end. This makes it necessary to pay attention to the

structure of the original sentence in the translation, in particular to the word order in it, and to translate it correctly. Translation of grammatical forms and constructions. In order to express the form and structure of the sentence in the original in the translation, it is first necessary to learn the features of the form and structure of the sentences in the original (English language) and translated language (Uzbek language). As mentioned above, the position of the participle in the sentence plays an important role in their form. If we pay attention to the use of simple verbs in simple sentences, in both languages. They will be as follows:

I am going to university today -Men bugun universitetga bormoqchiman

If we pay attention, we can see that in a simple Uzbek sentence, the participle always comes at the end of the sentence, and in English sentence, it comes in the second place.

Translation of articles. In order to solve the problem of translating an English article into Uzbek, it is necessary to clarify the characteristics of English articles first. In English, nouns are used with articles. The article defines the gender, number and conjugation of nouns. They are of two types: **definite** and **indefinite** articles. Translation of the indefinite article. Since the indefinite article comes in different positions in English, there are also different ways to translate it.

1) If we take the English word for tree, it is called *a tree*, and it is expressed as tree in Uzbek. When referring to it for the first time, it translates to *a tree- one tree*.

2) Indefinite article is used even if some quality is given to a specific person. For example, if we translate the sentence "She is a clever student" literally, a sentence like "U aqlli talaba" will appear.

3) Indefinite article can also be used when one specific subject is compared with another: *He looks like a professor-U professorga o'xshaydi*

4) After the English verbs *have/has*, the indefinite article is always used in the accusative case: *I have a book-Menda kitob bor*

Please note that the indefinite articles used in English sentences above are not translated into Uzbek!

Definite article translation. Depending on the use of specific articles in English, it is possible to determine the methods of their translation into Uzbek. Therefore, it is necessary to learn how to use them in the following cases:

1) Before the acquisition degree of adjectives: *Eldor Shomurodov is **the** best football player of Uzbekistan;*

2) Before the ordinal numbers: *This was **the** first novel of Isoqjon Nishonov.*

Definite articles in English are not translated into Uzbek, regardless of their use as above. More precisely, it is dropped. In translation, grammatical changes include: rearranging word groups, changing the position of clauses, replacing the neutral ratio with the definite ratio, including the addition and omitting words for grammatical purposes, and replacing compound sentences with a single sentence. In world translation studies, the term transformation is understood differently. A well-known Russian translation scientist's way of thinking about finding an alternative to the original linguistic unit's content, according to the particular situation. If a linguistic unit is dependent on the original text's structure, and finding an alternative corresponding to it in the translation becomes a transverse problem, he says it is called a **grammatical transformation**. Sullivan, a well-known translator, is a

member of the Oxford university press. Transformation is the use of other means, including the use of grammatical irregularities, according to Komissarov, when there is no other suitable alternative to the linguistic unit contained in the translation. Grammatical transformations are broken into three parts:

- 1) translating one original sentence into several sentences;
- 2) converting two original sentences into one sentence;
- 3) replacing the morphological or syntactic units used in the original sentence with other word groups in the translation, according to it. Sullivan, the third famous translator, is the third. Transformation is the original linguistic unit in the translated text, according to Barkhudarov.

Adjective and its degrees in English and Uzbek languages. It is a concept that expresses things, events, events, etc., according to their specific signs and internal characteristics, and in linguistics it is called a word group that expresses the sign of an object. Both languages have simple, comparative and superlative degrees of adjectives. Difference of the same sign in subjects in terms of more or less is called degrees of adjectives. Adjectives have the following degrees: ***simple degree, comparative degree and superlative degree.***

I. In simple adjectives, the sign is not comparable to the same sign in other subjects. This level indicates that the sign is normal and does not have a special indicator (addition): *a wide street, a green leaf, a good person.*

II. Comparative degree expresses that one sign in the subject is more than the same sign in another subject. The comparative degree is made by adding the suffix -er to the simple degree adjective, or by quoting the words each other, than, and more before the adjective:

1. *The apple tree is taller than the peach tree.*
2. *They are more beautiful than each other, even worse and stronger.*

III. Comparative degree expresses that the level of the sign has not reached the normal level, is lower than normal. The structure of degrees of adjective in English is different from Uzbek. The comparative degree is made by adding the suffix -er- to the simple degree.

For example: big-bigger, old-older, cheap-cheaper.

Hamburger is cheaper than hot-dog.

In English superlative degree of adjectives are made in two forms: **changeable** and **unchangeable**. The variable form is formed by adding the suffix (-est) the simple degree and is always used with the definite article: *cheap-the cheapest, old-the oldest, big-the biggest*

This is the biggest village.

There are a number of adjectives that are comparative degrees of adjectives that are not available for rules:

Good-well-the best

Bad-worse-the worst

Little-less-the least

Few-fewer-much

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